

**DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS THROUGH
ORGANIZING COMMUNICATIVE GAMES IN PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN****Nigmatullayeva Matluba**

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Annotation: In this article, there is an opinion on the development of communication skills in preschool children through the organization of communicative games. Development of preschool children's need for knowledge, inclination to study, regularly preparing them for the educational process through various games, development of games aimed at forming communication skills.

Key words: speech, communication, motive, communication, development, physical, children, organism, intellect.

In the preschool educational organization, the goal is to educate children in all aspects, that is, from the physical, mental, moral, aesthetic point of view. This goal is realized during the development of children's speech. As a result of developing oral speech in kindergarten, the child develops mentally and his general cultural level increases. He understands the surrounding events, laws of nature and society. The development of speech in a child helps him improve mentally. The child has the ability to learn about the outside world with the help of mental processes such as memory, imagination, imagination, thinking, as well as with the help of speech. However, children's intelligence, that is, mental processes (memory, imagination, imagination, thinking, etc.) do not appear only with the growth and improvement of the child's body, but also appear and improve with the development of speech.

If a child is taught to speak correctly from an early age, then such a child develops in a normal state, that is, the ability to imagine first, and then to think, imagine, and this ability improves with each age. Along with intelligence, mental processes such as will also develop in children. Many experiments show that a child whose speech is not developed does not develop as a complete person. Therefore, the educator should always remember that speech is a tool that helps children of preschool age to develop all mental processes. At the same time as teaching the child his native language, the ground is prepared for him to study successfully at school, he is taught to approach work creatively. In all educational activities of the kindergarten, children's speech is cultivated by teaching their mother tongue. In particular, speech development activities are planned for each child.

Speech development is necessary not only for familiarizing the child with the environment, but also for his general mental development.

We can cite the following as the tasks of speech formation and development:

- education of a child's emotional dependence and trust in adults;
- satisfy the need for positive attention of the surrounding people in relation to him;
- helping to develop the child's interests;

If we talk about children's communication in general, the quality aspect of communication of preschool children with their peers is changing compared to previous periods. For preschool children (4-5 years old), communication with peers becomes a priority. They actively communicate with each other in different situations (mode moments, in the course of different types of activities - play, work, work, etc.). Communication is especially evident and developed throughout the game. The developing dialogue develops depending on the nature of the game.

Communication with peers of preschool age takes the main place in the development of intellectual, speech, emotional and moral inclinations. Psychological, social and physical development of children depends on the development of relationships with peers. The main criteria of communication: attention and interest in the other, emotional attitude towards him, initiative and sensitivity. Communication is the emotional relationship of a person to a person. Therefore, communication with peers forms, develops and corrects the child's emotional sphere. Communication is a multifaceted process of development of communication between preschool children, born on the basis of cooperative activities and needs. Communication includes the exchange of information between the participants of cooperative activities, which is expressed in the communicative form of communication. People use language as a means of communication when entering into relationships with each other. The second aspect of communication is the interaction between the person who initiates the communication. In this, not only words are exchanged, but also actions and situations. For example, it is possible to communicate between a seller and a buyer without saying a word. The third aspect of communication is the perception of the interlocutors. It is important that the participants in the conversation understand each other correctly. Thus, three conditional moments of communication can be distinguished: communicative (giving information), interactive (interaction) and perceptive (mutual perception).

The unity of these three aspects of communication is manifested as a method of organizing the interaction and cooperative activities of preschool children who are engaged in communication. The purpose of the communication is to exchange information, establish mutual understanding and mutual relations with the students using various communication tools. The educational and didactic tasks of pedagogues cannot be carried out without ensuring the relationship between the teacher and the student community. During joint activities, people share different ideas, thoughts, and feelings. In this case, thoughts and feelings can be interpreted as information, and communication as information exchange. But interpersonal communication is not just an exchange of information. Because in the process of communication, information is not only transmitted, but also formed, clarified, developed.

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